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PROCEEDINGS

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MICROWAVE SINTERING OF ZNO-CONTAINING *IN-SITU* SPINELIZED ALUMINA-BASED CASTABLES

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ABSTRACT

Matching industrial activity and environmental protection is one of the toughest challenges of the 21st century. As high consumers of fossil-based materials, refractory manufacturers are consistently seeking processes that can provide higher energy efficiency. In this sense, using microwaves for ceramic sintering has shown significant advantages compared with the conventional route (based on electrical or natural gas heating), reducing lead time, enhancing mechanical properties, and demanding less power. However, this method has been underexplored for such application due to the lack of knowledge about refractory phases capable of effectively interacting with this type of electromagnetic radiation. Thus, this work addressed the potential of applying ZnO as a microwave absorber in Al₂O₃-based refractories, comparing microwave-sintered castables with electric-heated ones thermally treated up to 1700 °C. Although presenting a relatively high vapor pressure, the content of ZnO (11.4 wt%) remained stable at all temperatures applied in the electric-heated furnace, whereas significant evaporation was detected for samples microwaved above 1300 °C. The mechanisms related to this behavior and strategies to avoid it are discussed. On top of that, the microwave sintering method showed benefits such as higher densified microstructure with open pores remaining homogeneously scattered in the matrix, enhanced mechanical properties at room temperature, 26-fold faster lead time, and roughly-estimated 70%-lower energy consumption. Thus, this sintering method might be a promising alternative to increase the efficiency of refractory manufacturing, lowering environmental impacts and production costs.

INTRODUCTION

In a world with finite natural resources and where energy production fundamentally relies on the burning of fossil fuels, fulfilling the upcoming energy demand (47 % increase by 2050), ensuring environmental protection is considered one of the greatest challenges of this century¹. Regardless of introducing new non-polluting energy sources, it is believed that such a balance cannot be achieved without increasing the efficiency of the currently-used processes¹. Accounting for close to 12 % of all energy consumed worldwide², special attention must be given to industrial processes operating at high temperatures, such as the conventional sintering of ceramic materials. In this procedure, temperatures usually between 1000 °C and 2000 °C are applied for several hours to compact powder systems aiming at inducing the formation of ceramic bonds between the particles². Aiming at speeding up the sintering step and minimizing the energy consumed for it, different techniques have been developed in recent decades, such as microwave sintering². However, to be effective, this technique relies on the presence of phases capable of interacting with microwaves, converting the electric and/or magnetic fields into thermal energy, or even directly enhancing the diffusion process of the sintering mechanisms. These aspects depend on the materials' dielectric and magnetic properties and, for a broadly used ceramic oxide range (e.g. Al₂O₃, MgO and SiO₂) that are transparent to microwave at room temperatures, they do not allow microwave heating without using susceptors³. However, scaling up this sintering process to massive production, as is the case of refractories, remains a challenge³. Thus, adding microwave-absorbing compounds may foster using this sintering method for refractories and, as indicated by Bhattacharya and Basak⁴, zincite (ZnO) is a promising candidate due to its suitable microwave absorption.

Notwithstanding the changes led to the castables' properties, recent studies^{5,6} pointed out the feasibility of applying ZnO in alumina-

based castables as these oxides react at intermediate temperatures (~ 800 °C) forming a spinel-like phase with interesting properties (e.g. high refractoriness and low coefficient of thermal expansion). In this work, microwave-sintered ZnO-containing alumina-based vibrated castables were produced at different temperatures. Some of their key properties, microstructural features and energy demanded for sintering were assessed and compared to their conventionally fired counterparts.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The vibrated castables analysed in this work were produced with a packing distribution according to the modified Andreasen's model ($q = 0.26$) and following the procedure described in⁵. Calcined and tabular alumina (CL370 and T60/T64, Almatix, Germany) were used as Al₂O₃ sources, whereas 11.4 wt% of ZnO (analytical grade, Basile Química, Brazil) was added to induce the formation of 23.1 vol% (25.7 wt%) of ZnAl₂O₄ after firing. The castables were bonded with 6 wt% of calcium aluminate cement (CAC, Secar 71, Imerys Aluminates, France) and dispersed using 0.2 wt% of a commercial surfactant (Castament FS60, BASF, Germany), as shown in Tab. 1.

Tab. 1: Overall castable composition.

Raw material	wt%
Tabular alumina (<6 mm)	77.6
Calcined alumina (CL370)	5.0
Calcium aluminate cement	6.0
ZnO	11.4

This dry mixture was firstly homogenized for 5 minutes in special rheometer equipment designed to process refractory castables, followed by the addition of 3.8 wt% of distilled water. The fresh suspension was molded into bars (25 mm x 25 mm x 150 mm), cured in a climatic chamber (VC 2020, Vötsch, Germany) for 24 h under 50 °C and 80 % of relative humidity, dried at 110 °C for another 24 h, and calcined at 600 °C for 5 h.

The calcined samples were then sintered at different temperatures up to 1600 °C using a conventional electric furnace (model BF51314C, cavity capacity of 2.5 L, Lindberg/blue, USA) or up to 1700 °C in microwave equipment (model MS6K, multimode cavity, 2.45GHz, useful cavity capacity of ~ 3 L, Cober Electronics, USA) with effective power (also referred to as non-reflected or forward power) up to 4 kW and silicon carbide as susceptors⁴. In the former case, a constant heating rate of 2 °Cmin⁻¹ and a dwell time of 5 h was applied, whereas for the latter, 50 °Cmin⁻¹ up to 1100 °C and 20 °Cmin⁻¹ above it, and dwell time of 15 minutes at the selected temperature, was used. To ensure proper temperature control, a type-B thermocouple (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) or a pyrometer (MA2S, Marathon Series, Raytek, USA) were applied in the conventional and microwave equipment, respectively. Moreover, the electric power required for the set firing schedule in both furnaces was tracked down using the potentiometer embodied in each piece of equipment (BF51314C and MS6K, for the electric and microwave furnaces, respectively).

The previously described sintering conditions gave rise to the nomenclature system, depicted in Tab. 2. After the sintering step, all samples had their mass loss assessed with an analytical balance (model TS400D, Ohaus, USA). Young's modulus was measured by the non-destructive sonic resonance technique (Scanelastic equipment, ATCP Physical engineering, Brazil). Cold modulus of rupture (CMOR) was carried out in MTS 810 equipment (MTS Systems, USA) under 3-point bending (ASTM C133 – 97) and

using 8 specimens for each sintering temperature. Quantitative mineralogical content was conducted by applying Rietveld's refinement (Topas software, version 4.2, Bruker, USA) on the X-ray diffraction patterns (D8 Focus, Bruker, Germany) obtained for grounded samples. Open porosity and density were evaluated by the immersion method based on Archimedes' principle and using kerosene as liquid media (ASTM C830-00). Based on the samples' density and the theoretical density considering the quantitative phase content (XRD), the total porosity was estimated. The microstructure of some selected samples was evaluated by scanning electron microscopy (Inspect S50, FEI, USA) coupled with an energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscope (EDS). Additionally, thermodynamic calculations (FactSage 6.4, CRCT, Canada) were carried out to assess the oxygen partial pressure (p_{O_2}) inside the microwave cavity during the sintering.

Tab. 2: Nomenclature used for the distinct sintering methods.

Firing Method	Maximum temperature	Nomenclature
Electric furnace	1150 °C	EF-1150
	1300 °C	EF-1300
	1500 °C	EF-1500
Microwave	1150 °C	MW-1150
	1300 °C	MW-1300
	1500 °C	MW-1500
	1700 °C	MW-1700

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Aiming at addressing the effect of the sintering method on the microstructure of the castable, the total and open porosity were measured and are depicted in Fig. 1. For conventional firing, it could be seen that the increase in the thermal treatment temperature resulted in a decrease in both open and total porosity, especially in the former. Additionally, for the same sintering process a general trend between total and open porosity could be seen (indicated by the red dotted line), in which the total porosity scales with the open porosity. This behaviour is expected for this traditional sintering technique as the densification process will usually act similarly on open and closed pores located among the particles (whereas pores within the grains require much higher energy to be eliminated), reducing their amount³.

Fig. 1: Open and total porosity of rupture for conventional (EF) and microwave (MW) sintered castables. Adapted from Ref. 12 with Elsevier permission (n° 5577640295991).

As higher heating rates favoured the densification process rather than grain coarsening, a more significant reduction in both types of pores was expected for microwave sintering⁷. Nevertheless, for these samples, the increment in the sintering temperature led to a significant total porosity decrease, as expected, but with an open porosity increase. Therefore, although more effective to densify the castable composition evaluated in this work, the microwave heating technique also induced a higher number of open pores. It is worth highlighting that this additional open porosity is not necessarily detrimental to the castables' properties. On one hand, if they are small and well dispersed, these open pores can induce fracture energy increase by crack branching and/or increasing the crack tip curvature radius⁸. On the other hand, if coarse and preferentially

located, this open porosity will act as critical defects and paths for slag infiltration, reducing the mechanical and corrosion resistances. To evaluate the impact of each sintering condition on the mechanical properties of the castable, Young's modulus (E) and cold modulus of rupture (CMOR) tests were carried out and are presented in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: Elastic modulus and cold modulus of rupture. Adapted from Ref. 12 with Elsevier permission (n° 5577640295991).

Analysing these results, one can see a clear relationship between E and CMOR for both sintering techniques. Additionally, although increasing the sintering temperature resulted in enhanced mechanical properties for conventional and microwave-sintered samples, this effect was much more significant for the latter. The joint analyses of Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 points out, as expected, that the total porosity plays a major role on the mechanical strength. Therefore, the significant densification led by microwave sintering resulted in samples with higher E and CMOR, which is attributed to the higher heating rate and enhanced ion diffusion induced by this sintering technique². Note that the samples sintered by microwave radiation at 1150 °C for 15 minutes presented equivalent strength to those conventionally fired at 1500 °C for 5 hours. Thus, while the conventional sintering (1500 °C) lasted 17.5 h to complete the firing schedule, the microwave heating (1150 °C) required less than 40 minutes to produce castables with similar E and CMOR, which is twenty-six-fold faster.

Besides the time saving, the energy consumption to manufacture the specimens was also highly impacted by the firing method. Fig. 3 shows the energy required to run the sintering procedure in the electric furnace (2 °Cmin⁻¹ up to 1500 °C and 5h of dwell time) and in the microwave one (50 °Cmin⁻¹ up to 1100 °C and 20 °Cmin⁻¹ above it, with a dwell time of 15 minutes). Analysing it, one can see that the conventional furnace demanded 3.5 kWh per sample, whereas the microwave consumed 1 kWh per sample, which is ~ 70 % lower. This higher efficiency can be attributed to the lack of energy loss for heating up the air and insulating refractories inside the microwave equipment. Conversely, in conventional heating, all the systems (air and refractories included) will reach high temperatures, implying higher energy losses².

Fig. 3: Energy demanded for each bar sample to be sintered (● denotes the end of the firing process). Adapted from Ref. 12 with Elsevier permission (n° 5577640295991).

Therefore, to reach equivalent E and CMOR in the analysed system, the microwave sintering (1150 °C / 15 min) was 26-fold faster and 70 % more energy-efficient than the conventional electric-heated equipment (1500 °C / 5 h). Although these are eye-catching features, it is worth noticing that suitable E and CMOR are

just two of several other key properties that must be fulfilled by the refractory material, depending on the application. Therefore, further analyses are required to assess the feasibility of applying such a sintering technique to a broad production of refractories. Moving forward on these characterizations, the microstructural changes resulting from the distinct sintering methods were evaluated by BSE/SEM, depicted in Fig. 4, of samples thermally treated at 1150 °C and 1500 °C. It is worth noticing that the comparison between samples produced by both sintering techniques must consider that the microwaves electromagnetic fields affect samples' thermodynamic stability and enhance the ion mobility⁹. On top of that, the quite distinct heating rate used for each sintering technique also helps to induce different microstructures, as previously reported by several other authors³.

Fig. 4: Microstructure of samples sintered at 1150 °C or 1500 °C assessed by SEM/BSE. Adapted from Ref. 12 with Elsevier permission (n° 5577640295991).

Initially, firing at 1150 °C by both sintering methods resulted in similar microstructures comprised of well-defined alumina aggregates with ZnAl_2O_4 formed in the matrix, which also presented several pores and undensified regions attributed to the significant Kirkendall effect undergone by this composition⁵. As the temperature increases to 1500 °C, some distinctions between the heating methods stand out. In tune with total porosity analysis (Fig. 1), the conventionally fired samples remained with a less densified gahnite-based matrix. Moreover, at 1500 °C, the samples also presented acicular-grown calcium hexaluminate ($\text{CaO} \cdot 6\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ or CA_6) as a result of the calcium aluminate cement (CAC) addition. On the other hand, for the microwave sintering, heating at 1500 °C led remarkable microstructural changes, with nodular-like CA_6 formation in a highly densified matrix containing spherical pores. These types of microstructures agree with the porosity results presented in Fig. 1, in which the microwave sintering was more effective to reduce total porosity, but induced the formation of a higher number of open pores.

Aiming at assessing the mechanism that led to this open porosity increase for the microwave sintering, calcined samples had their mass loss analyzed after subsequent thermal treatments, as shown in Fig. 5 (a). At temperatures in the range of 1150 °C up to 1500 °C, no appreciable mass loss was detected for conventionally fired samples, which is assigned to the lack of organic or hydrated phases, as they were decomposed in the calcining step. However, the mass loss faced by microwave-heated samples stood out. Firing at 1500 °C and 1700 °C in the microwave equipment resulted in a mass decrease of 1.3 wt% and 4.3 wt%, respectively. To track down the causes of these mass losses, quantitative XRD were conducted and Fig. 5 (b) depicts the changes in gahnite content for the conventionally- or microwave-heated samples.

Fig. 5: (a) Mass variation after firing; (b) ZnAl_2O_4 (gahnite) content measured by quantitative XRD. Adapted from Ref. 12 with Elsevier permission (n° 5577640295991).

Conversely to the conventional firing, in which gahnite was stable at all analyzed temperatures, the microwave heating led to partial gahnite decomposition at 1500 °C and 1700 °C. Moreover, as no other Zn-containing phase was detected and the reduction in ZnAl_2O_4 content took place along with alumina content increase, gahnite decomposition could have happened by the Zn volatilization, which was withdrawn from the spinel structure as gaseous zinc, leaving Al_2O_3 behind. The zinc removal from the spinel structure was already studied in the literature, especially applied to zinc recovery from the blast furnace dust, which presented up to 5 wt% of zinc ferrite (ZnFe_2O_4) and gahnite (ZnAl_2O_4) in its composition¹⁰. Nevertheless, in that dust, zinc volatilization just takes place close to 1300 °C at reducing atmospheres¹⁰. Although neither the electric furnace nor the microwave equipment had a controlled atmosphere, the latter presented susceptors made out of silicon carbide, which could be oxidized at high temperatures leading to a reducing environment inside the microwave chamber.

To evaluate this hypothesis, a piece of the silicon carbide susceptor used for a single sintering (1500 °C / 15 min) in the microwave equipment [a picture of distinct pieces before and after such thermal treatment can be seen in Fig. 6] had its transversal sectioning evaluated by SEM, depicted in Fig. 6. A SiO_2 layer on the surface of the SiC susceptor was observed and its mean thickness measured was 64.9 µm. Based on this oxidative reaction zone, a $p\text{O}_2$ down to 10^{-15} atm and 10^{-13} atm are foreseen by the thermodynamic simulation to be formed inside the microwave chamber at 1500 °C and 1700 °C, respectively. Therefore, although experimental measurements are required to precisely determine the real $p\text{O}_2$ -value during the microwave sintering, it can be inferred that the SiC oxidation will lead to a reducing atmosphere inside the microwave chamber during sintering.

Fig. 6: Distinct SiC-based susceptors pieces before (as received) and after the microwave treatment up to 1500 °C for 15 minutes under uncontrolled atmosphere, and SEM image of the SiO_2 layer formed on the SiC susceptor surface after one heating at 1500 °C for 15 minutes. Adapted from Ref. 12 with Elsevier permission (n° 5577640295991).

As previously discussed, well-distributed small pores in the highly densified matrix of the castable are not necessarily undesirable. However, for some applications in which the castable will be in contact with molten media (slag or metal), these open pores can increase the susceptibility to corrosion. Thus, a likely strategy to merge the high strength (E and CMOR) provided by the microwave sintering at higher temperatures ($> 1300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) with the minimization of the open porosity is attained by applying a purging gas flow inside the microwave chamber to reduce the SiC oxidation, avoiding the formation of a reducing atmosphere during the firing procedure. To assess such an approach, argon (Ar, analytical grade) was used to continuously purge the microwave chamber (flux of 1.5 L min^{-1}) when heating at $1500\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 15 min, resulting in the castable microstructure depicted in Fig. 7. Although not fully avoided, the porosity created due to ZnO volatilization was minimized and the mean size of the pores was reduced. Compared to the samples fired at the same temperature and dwell time, but without atmospheric control, lower mass loss after sintering (0.65 wt% vs. 1.3 wt%), a decrease in the total and open porosity (21.2 % and 16.4 % vs. 22.9 % and 18.7 %, respectively), higher E (154 GPa vs. 142 GPa) and improved CMOR (48 MPa vs. 41.4 MPa), were achieved. Moreover, another interesting aspect was the formation of the ZnAl_2O_4 phase within the alumina aggregates. Thus, conversely to the microstructure obtained for the microwaved samples ($1500\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} / 15\text{ min}$) in an uncontrolled atmosphere, the gahnite formed inside the alumina aggregates could be preserved in a saturated argon environment.

Fig. 7: Microstructure (SEM/BSE) of microwaved samples processed at $1500\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 15 minutes under a controlled atmosphere (Argon, 1.5 L min^{-1}). Adapted from Ref. 12 with Elsevier permission (n° 5577640295991).

These results indicate that the zinc volatilization was minimized by controlling the atmosphere during the microwave sintering, but it was not completely halted. Two non-mutually exclusive mechanisms could explain such behaviour: (i) the electromagnetic microwave fields imposed on the sample at high temperatures may change the thermodynamic stability of zinc in the structure (it is worth noticing that all thermodynamic calculations were conducted considering no electromagnetic fields due to the lack of data under such conditions); (ii) the gas flux applied (1.5 L min^{-1}) increased the pO_2 during the sintering, but it was not enough to avoid the formation of a reducing atmosphere. The evaluation of such a hypothesis requires further analysis, however, for the second case, replacing silicon carbide susceptors by oxide materials could be a suitable way to avoid a reducing atmosphere during the microwave sintering procedure⁴. In this sense, some promising alternatives are being evaluated.

CONCLUSIONS

The feasibility of applying microwave sintering to ZnO-containing alumina-based castables bonded with CAC was assessed using SiC susceptors up to $1700\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ with a dwell time of 15 minutes. To enable comparisons, conventionally fired samples were produced in an electric furnace after sintering for 5h at selected temperatures. Due to the higher heating rate and enhanced ion mobility provided

by the microwave technique, denser (lower total porosity) and stronger (higher E and CMOR) samples were produced in a much faster and 70% less energy consuming sintering procedure. The microwave processing also induced an increase in open pore content, as shown by SEM micrographs. The pores were relatively small in size and homogeneously scattered in the matrix of the castable, which could positively impact some thermomechanical properties. Despite these worthwhile aspects, mass loss and quantitative XRD indicated zinc volatilization for microwave samples heated above $1300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in air. When a purging inert gas flux was applied to the microwave sintering up to $1500\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, mass losses were significantly decreased, corroborating the hypothesis that a reducing atmosphere is fostering such ZnO volatilization. Therefore, even though some parameters must be optimized, the present work highlights that microwave radiation could be applied to thermally treat some pre-shaped refractory compositions, leading to environmental, productivity and performance benefits.

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